

Burnout Syndrome and Depression among Medical Students: A Cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Background: Burnout is defined as a mental, psychological, and physical state of chronic fatigue, depression, and frustration, typically caused by commitment to duties that did not realize the person's ambitions and expected rewards. There is an overlap between burnout and depression, or burnout probably might be a risk factor of developing depression **Objectives:** To assess the prevalence of burnout syndrome and depression among medical students and underlying causes. **Methodology:** This was a cross-sectional study. Data were gathered using an online form questionnaire filled out by medical students of different academic years from Benha faculty of medicine. The questionnaire included questions about respondents' demographics, and 11 questions concerning burnout (BUT) and 9 questions about depression. Overall, 406 participants were included in the study. **Results:** The prevalence of BUT among the participants is 24.9%, while the prevalence of depression among them is 83.3%. The BUT score is affected by residence and academic year the depression score is affected by gender and academic year. **Conclusion:** Depression among medical students in Benha Faculty of Medicine is highly prevalent. A lesser, yet cannot be ignored, prevalence of burnout is also present. Depression can vary

according to gender or academic year, while burnout can vary according to residence or academic year.

Keywords: Burnout, Medical students, Depression, Benha

Introduction

Stress and its complications are huge problems, regardless of the relativity of stress as a human experience, and the fact that there is no exact measure or definition of stress. Generally, stress is the physical and normal response of body to things that makes people feel worried and bothered ⁽¹⁾. Stress is not abnormal, nor something to be avoided. It is already a motivating and stimulating part of life, that can manifest at any point in one's life ⁽¹⁾.

A complication of stress if it was poorly dealt with is a state called Burnout. Burnout is defined as a mental, psychological, and physical state of chronic fatigue, depression, and frustration, typically caused by commitment to duties that did not realize the person's ambitions and expected rewards ⁽²⁾. Symptoms and signs of burnout can be classified into two main categories: First: Affective symptoms: Typically, a gloomy, tearful, and depressed mood is observed among those who suffer from burnout. Although moods may change quickly, but the general state is low, sad and the dim mood prevails. Second: Cognitive symptoms: Thinking in a helpless, hopeless, and power-less attitude ⁽³⁾.

It had been proved that there is correlation between burnout and depression. There is an overlap between burnout and depression, or burnout probably might be a risk factor of developing depression ⁽⁴⁾. Although burnout and depression appear to share some common features, several researchers believe that burnout and depression are two separate psychological and mental phenomena ⁽⁵⁾ and that

emotional exhaustion is not related to depression ⁽⁶⁾. Furthermore, one major factor that appears to distinguish burnout from depression is the fact that burnout is work related and situation specific, whereas depression is context free and pervasive ⁽⁷⁾.

It is undeniable that burnout and depression are affected by similar and closely related factors. Burnout and depressive symptoms have been found to change together over time⁽⁸⁾.

Medical schools around the globe have long been considered stressful environments for students and future practitioners. Previous research has identified long hours of study, and the impact of emotional burden, high workload, and others ⁽⁹⁾.

Hence, it is not shocking that medical students have been found to show a higher prevalence of depressive symptoms and burnout episodes than the general population ⁽¹⁰⁾. The importance of conducting this research emerged from here, as a way to better understand the factors that put medical students' mental health in danger, and to better understand what changes should be done to save the mental health and well-being of the future generations of doctors and healthcare workforce.

Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted on medical students of different academic years from Benha Faculty of Medicine, Egypt during the period from November 2021 to January 2022.

Sampling: The sample size was calculated using Epi info. It was based on a prevalence of depression among medical students of 46.5% ⁽¹¹⁾ and confidence limit of 5% and power of 80%. The minimum required sample size at 95% confidence level was 383 medical students. We increased number of participants in the study by 6% of sample size to increase the power of the study. So, the total participants that were included in the study is 406 participants. **Tool of data collection:** A pre-

designed and coded questionnaire in English language was filled by the students. The data was collected through online Google form which included three sections. The first section included socio-demographic data. The second section was a modified version of the BCSQ-12-SS "Burnout Clinical Subtype Questionnaire Students Survey". BCSQ-12-SS is a short version of the "Burnout Clinical Subtype Questionnaire", or BCSQ-12. The modified version of BCSQ-12-SS is composed of 11 items⁽¹²⁾ that were already distributed throughout the dimensions. : "overload" (e.g., "I think I invest more than is healthy in my commitment to my studies"), "lack of development" (e.g., "I would like to study something else that would be more challenging to my abilities"), and "neglect" (e.g., "When the results of my studies are not good at all, I stop making an effort"). After conducting a pilot study, the modification procedure of BCSQ-12-SS included removing two questions: ("I feel that my current studies are hampering the development of my abilities", and "I give up in response to an obstacle in my studies") and adding another two questions: ("I am putting my health in danger to pursue good results in my studies") and ("Online learning reduced my passion towards my studies"). Three experts from Public Health and Community Medicine Department had assessed the questionnaire after modification. Also, Cronbach's alpha test was done for this section, which showed high validity (0.737). The participants were required to indicate how much they agreed with each statement using a Likert-type scale with 7 response options ranging from 1 "completely disagree" (meaning lower score of burnout) to 7 "completely agree" (meaning higher score of burnout), with total score from 11 – 77. In the third section, the participants responded to the "Patient Health Questionnaire"⁽¹³⁾, or PHQ-9. In this part of questions our aim was to find out the presence and the severity of depression. Those questions measure the presence of nine diagnostic criteria based on the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual Disorder-IV. Cronbach's alpha test was done, which showed high validity (0.822). The responses range from 0 "not at

all" (meaning lower score of depression), to 3 "nearly every day" (meaning higher score of depression), with total score from 0 - 27. **Data management:** All statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS, version 25 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). Numerical data will be described in the form of median \pm IQR (Interquartile range). Categorical data were described in the form of frequencies and percentages. Quantitative data were tested for normality using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant, and a p-value < 0.01 was considered highly significant. Mann-Whitney, Kruskal-Wallis and Wilcoxon signed rank tests are non-parametric tests which are used to compare between different groups.

Results

Table (1) and Figure (1) shows that the median of age of study participants is 20.0 years. Females represent the higher proportion (66.0%), while the males show the lower proportion (34.0%). The table also illustrates that more than half of study group are rural residents (60.3%). The students are almost equally represented from different academic years with highest percentage 3rd academic year (24.9%). The median of BUT score is 47.0, while for depression score, the median is 16.0. The table shows that 24.9% of participants have high BUT score, and 83.3% have high depression score.

Table (2) clarifies that there is statistically significant difference between males and females as regard depression score (p value= 0.015) with a higher median is for females in comparison with males (16.0 vs 14.5 respectively), while BUT score doesn't show significant difference between the two groups (p value=0.231). The table demonstrates that there is statistically significant difference in BUT score according to residence (p value =0.014). Higher median of the score is for rural residents (48.0). While depression score doesn't show any significant difference (p value = 0.362). The table also displays that there is statistically significant difference

between students from different academic year as regard both BUT and depression scores (p value <0.001, =0.001 respectively). The 6th year students show the highest median for BUT score (53.0). While all of 2nd, 6th and intern students show the highest median for depression score (17.0).

Table (3) illustrates that there is no significant correlation between age of participants and their BUT as well as depression score.

Table (4) and Figure (2) shows that there is highly statistically significant positive weak correlation between BUT and depression scores (Rho=0.492, p value<0.001). This means that increase in BUT score is associated with increase in depression score.

Univariate and multivariate analysis shows that only depression score is the only predictor of BUT score (**Table 5**).

Univariate analysis shows that male gender, 1st academic year as well as BUT score can significantly predict depression score, while multivariate analysis shows that only 1st academic year as well as BUT score can significantly predict depression score (**Table 6**).

Discussion

A) BUT score

Our study revealed that the prevalence of BUT among the participants is 24.9%. This finding nearly similar to *Galan et al., 2011*⁽¹⁴⁾ a study was done in Spain who revealed that the prevalence of BUT among the participants is 37.5%. On contrary *Fares et al., 2015*⁽¹⁵⁾ found that 75% of students suffered from burnout. This variation between studies can be attributed to the difference in teaching methods, educational curricula as well as exams between different medical schools.

This study showed that there's no statistically significant difference as regard BUT between male and female. *Cecil et al., 2014* ⁽¹⁶⁾ reported no significant difference between percentage of BUT and gender. Similarly, *Chin et al., 2016* ⁽¹⁷⁾ found that analysis showed no significant association between prevalence of burnout and gender. This comes against *Paro et al., 2014* ⁽¹⁸⁾ who observed different burnout score patterns between genders. Higher scores for emotional exhaustion were noted among female students, whereas higher scores for depersonalization were found among males. It was found that there is a discrepancy between the number of females and males who suffer from burnout, as the percentage of females increased more, and this appeared in the presence of difficulties in dealing with some pressures in study and work. Women with burnout reported a higher rate of impaired awakening, lower job control, greater proportion of unpaid work and worked to a greater extent "with people" compared to men. Men with burnout had a more restricted social network and reported working more overtime than women. Patients with burnout reported a higher rate of unemployment, a more restricted social network and higher work demands compared to a general population.

Our study shows that there is statistically significant difference in BUT score as regard residence, which is higher for urban residents. Similarly, *El-Masry et al., 2013* ⁽¹⁹⁾ found that residence is a significant predictor of BUT score, with a higher percentage for urban residents. But *Atlam, 2018* ⁽²⁰⁾ in Egypt revealed that rural residents have higher percentage of personal burnout than urban ones and this difference was statistically significant. On the other side, work burnout showed no significant difference.

The study reveals the most vulnerable group for BUT is 6th year students, which is significantly different. *Paro et al., 2014* ⁽¹⁸⁾ found significant difference between different domains of burnout and the academic year, with a higher mean in

all domains for 5th and 6th year students (17). This is inconsistent with *Cecil et al., 2014*⁽¹⁶⁾ reported no significant difference between percentage of BUT and year of study. Along with *Chin et al., 2016*⁽¹⁷⁾ who revealed that analysis showed no significant association between prevalence of burnout and respective year of study.

B) Depression score

This study revealed that the prevalence of depression among the participants is 83.3%. *Shams-Eldin et al., 2019*⁽²¹⁾ found that prevalence of depression is 42.9%. This disagrees with, *Sidana et al., 2012*⁽²²⁾ who showed that only 21.5% of students suffer from depression. Along with, *Basnet, et al., 2012*⁽²³⁾ who showed that only 29.78% of students suffer from depression

The study showed that there's a statistically significant difference as regard depression between male and female with a higher median for female. This agrees with *Abdallah, 2014*⁽²⁴⁾ reported significant associations between the presence of depression and gender. Similarly, *Shams-Eldin et al., 2019*⁽²¹⁾ which find that depression was significantly more prevalent among female students. But this disagrees with *Basnet, et al., 2012*⁽²³⁾ who found that there was no statistically significant difference between males and females as regard incidence of depression. Also, *Sidana et al., 2012*⁽²²⁾ found that there was no statistically significant difference between males and females as regard incidence of depression. We also noted that there is a discrepancy between the ratio of females suffering from depression or fatigue to males among the studies. In some studies, the ratio between females to males was as large as (48.4: 22.1) %, and in some other universities such as *Shams-Eldin et al., 2019*⁽²¹⁾, the ratio of females to males was close to (46.4: 39.5) %. We can also attribute the disparity between the rates of depression and fatigue among females and males between research to the difference in customs and societal

pressures from one place to another, and because of the physiological nature of females, which may make them more vulnerable to stress.

This study shows that there's no statistically significant difference in depression score as regard residence. This comes against *Abdallah, 2014*⁽²⁴⁾ who reported that students who are resident in rural areas were more liable to get depressed and distressed than their peers from urban areas. And this difference is statistically significant.

The study reveals the most vulnerable groups for depression are 2nd, 6th, and intern. which is significantly different. *Basnet, et al., 2012*⁽²³⁾ reported that the prevalence of depression was found to be more among the first-year students than the third-year students. *Sidana et al., 2012*⁽²²⁾ found that there was statistically significant difference between students of different academic years and the score of depression. *Fawzy & Hamed, 2017*⁽²⁵⁾ found that the prevalence of depression was significantly higher among pre-clinical years students compared to clinical years students. *Shams-Eldin et al., 2019*⁽²¹⁾ found that the prevalence of depression was significantly higher among basic sciences level students (2nd and 3rd study years) compared to clinical sciences level students (4th, 5th, and 6th study years). It is possible to attribute the difference in rates of depression according to academic years to the difference in the teaching system, curricula, and examination system between universities, which could make the study burdens on some students of academic years more than their peers from other universities, which will increase the rates of depression and burnout.

Conclusion

Burnout and depression are major threats to the wellbeing and performance of the future workforce that will be on the front lines. Medical students usually suffer

from university-related stress which causes them depression and burnout that significantly affects their performance ⁽⁹⁾.

High percentage of medical students from Benha Faculty of Medicine suffer from high scores of depression. Although high scores of burnout are not as prevalent as depression, its presence also creates a threat to the general state of students. Female, 6th year, and intern students are more susceptible to depression. Students who live in rural areas and -again- 6th year students have higher levels of burnout. Longitudinal assessment of such problems as well as more powerful studies are needed to further investigate medical student's wellbeing. Such studies will help act early and quickly to solve this problem. We also need to investigate what particularly causes medical students to burnout or feel depressed.

Limitations of the study

First, the study was conducted on a single medical school which limits the power of the study. Second, the tool of data collection was a questionnaire which is considered a subjective not objective tool for assessment. Furthermore, this study compared students who presented burnout from different school years, but a longitudinal assessment of these students would be a more appropriate approach.

Recommendations

Our research shows that burnout and depression are quite prevailing among medical students in Benha University and has also revealed higher depression rates among female students. Further research should be taken into consideration to sort out factors behind such results. Association between mental exhaustion and social factors should be considered. We also recommend studies to be done not only on the various factors contributing to depression among medical students, but also factors that might exacerbate such condition. Our study hasn't concluded any need to

change in teaching styles or scheduling, yet we believe that additional studies are required to confirm these findings. Strategies to reduce burnout among students should be discussed as students should have more time for stress relieving activities. Moreover, skills such as emotional expression and constructive reinterpretation should be encouraged among students. Further recommendations include motivating student-led services in Benha University to offer mentorship for freshmen and junior students on stress and time management. Besides arranging extracurricular activities that can help inspire students and boost their self-esteem.

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Table (1): Distribution of study participants according to their socio-demographic characteristics and their Burnout (BUT) and depression score

Variable	Total no=406	
	Median	IQR*
Age (years)	20.0	19.0-21.0
BUT score	47.0	39.8-55.3
Depression score	16.0	11.0-20.0

*IQR= interquartile range

Figure (1): Distribution of study participants according to their socio-demographic characteristics and their Burnout (BUT) and depression score

* BUT score= Burnout score

High score' implies scores higher than the upper quartile of the scores observed in the sample', 'low score' implies scores lower than or equal to the upper quartile ⁽¹²⁾

** Depression score= A cutoff score of 10 is used, so the score was considered high if it is equal to or higher than 10 ⁽¹³⁾

Table (2): Comparing BUT and depression scores of study participants according to some personal data

Variable		BUT score	Depression score	
Gender	Male (n=138)	Median	46.0	14.5
		IQR	38.0-55.0	10.0-18.0
	Female (n=268)	Median	48.0	16.0
		IQR	40.0-56.0	12.0-20.0
	Man-Whitney U test		17151.0	15779.0
	p value		0.231 (NS)*	0.015 (S)**
Residence	Urban (n=161)	Median	44.0	15.0
		IQR	38.0-54.0	11.0-19.5
	Rural (n=245)	Median	48.0	41.0-56.0
		IQR	16.0	11.0-20.0
	Man-Whitney U test		16867.5	18669.0
	p value		0.014 (S)	0.362 (NS)
Academic year	1st	Median	44.0	16.0
		IQR	37.0-56.0	11.0-20.5
	2nd	Median	51.5	17.0
		IQR	44.0-57.7	14.0-21.0
	3rd	Median	45.0	14.0
		IQR	38.5-51.0	10.0-17.0
	4th	Median	47.0	15.0
		IQR	39.3-55.8	10.0-19.0
	5th	Median	42.0	16.0
		IQR	38.0-48.0	11.0-20.0
	6th	Median	53.0	17.0
		IQR	49.5-59.0	14.3-19.8
	Intern	Median	51.0	17.0
		IQR	42.5-61.0	12.0-21.0
KW test***		29.1	22.9	
p value		<0.001 (HS)****	0.001 (HS)	

*NS = non-significant

**S = significant

***KW test= Kruskal Wallis test

****HS =Highly significant

Table (3): Correlation between age of participants and their BUT and depression scores

Variable	Age	
	Rho*	P
BUT score	0.012	0.817 (NS)
Depression score	-0.041	0.406 (NS)

*Rho = spearman correlation coefficient

Table (4): Correlation between BUT and depression scores

Variable	BUT score	
	Rho	P
Depression score	0.492	<0.001 (HS)

Figure (2): Scatter diagram show positive correlation between BUT and depression scores

Table (5): Univariate and multivariate logistic regression analysis for the predictors of high and low BUT score

Variable	Univariate logistic regression				Multivariate logistic regression			
	β	Crude OR	95%CI	P	β	Adjusted OR	95%CI	P
Age	0.01	1.0	0.9-1.1	0.889 (NS)	-0.1	0.9	0.6-1.4	0.711(NS)
Male gender	0.2	1.2	0.8-2.0	0.420 (NS)	-0.1	0.9	0.5-1.6	0.760(NS)
1 st academic year	0.6	1.7	0.8-3.7	0.8160(NS)	-0.5	1.7	0.7-4.2	0.272(NS)
Rural residence	-0.1	0.9	0.6-1.4	0.630 (NS)	0.1	0.9	0.5-1.5	0.635 (NS)
Depression score	0.2	1.2	1.1-1.3	<0.001 (HS)	0.2	1.2	1.1-1.3	<0.001 (HS)

Table (6): Univariate and multivariate logistic regression analysis for the predictors of high and low depression score

Variable	Univariate logistic regression				Multivariate logistic regression			
	β	Crude OR	95%CI	P	β	Adjusted OR	95%CI	P
Age	-0.1	0.9	0.8-1.1	0.338 (NS)	-0.1	0.9	0.5-1.5	0.635 (NS)
Male gender	0.7	1.9	1.1-3.3	0.014 (S)	-0.6	1.8	1.0-3.4	0.069 (NS)
1 st academic year	1.7	5.4	1.6-18.6	0.007 (S)	1.6	4.9	1.2-19.6	0.026 (S)
Rural residence	0.1	0.9	0.5-1.5	0.581 (NS)	0.3	1.4	0.7-2.5	0.312(NS)
BUT score	0.1	1.1	1.1-1.2	<0.001 (HS)	0.1	1.1	1.1-1.2	<0.001 (HS)